

Self-dual vector spaces

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Let K be a field, V a K -vector space, $\mathrm{GL}(V)$ the automorphism group of V , and $V^* := \mathrm{Hom}_K(V, K)$ the dual of V , equipped with its natural $\mathrm{GL}(V)$ -module structure. Say that V is **self-dual** if there is a $\mathrm{GL}(V)$ -module isomorphism $V \simeq V^*$.

The purpose of this text is to answer the question: which vector spaces are self-dual?

A necessary condition is that V be finite dimensional (this follows from the Erdős–Kaplansky Theorem), and a sufficient condition is that V be the zero vector space. So, from now on we assume that V is nonzero and finite dimensional. We denote the dimension of V by n (note $n \geq 1$), and the cardinality of K by κ .

Theorem. *The vector space V is self-dual if and only if $\kappa + n \leq 4$. Moreover $\dim \mathrm{Hom}_{\mathrm{GL}(V)}(V, V^*)$ depends only on κ and n . Denoting this integer by $d(\kappa, n)$, we have $d(\kappa, n) = 1$ if $\kappa + n \leq 4$, and $d(\kappa, n) = 0$ otherwise. (Recall that we assume $V \neq 0$.)*

Loosely speaking: the only nonzero self-dual vector spaces are $\mathbb{F}_2, \mathbb{F}_3$ and $(\mathbb{F}_2)^2$. The unique $\mathrm{GL}((\mathbb{F}_2)^2)$ -isomorphism $\phi : (\mathbb{F}_2)^2 \rightarrow ((\mathbb{F}_2)^2)^*$ is given by

$$\left(\phi \begin{pmatrix} a \\ c \end{pmatrix} \right) \begin{pmatrix} b \\ d \end{pmatrix} = \det \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} = ad + bc.$$

Let us add for completeness sake that, for κ equal to 2 or 3, a $\mathrm{GL}(\mathbb{F}_\kappa)$ -isomorphism $\psi : \mathbb{F}_\kappa \rightarrow (\mathbb{F}_\kappa)^*$ is given by $(\psi(x))(y) = xy$.

Note that $\mathrm{Hom}_{\mathrm{GL}(V)}(V, V^*)$ is isomorphic to the space $B(V)$ of $\mathrm{GL}(V)$ -invariant bilinear forms on V .

To prove the theorem, it suffices to verify the statement about $d(\kappa, n)$. The case $n = 1$ is left to the reader as an easy exercise. So we suppose from now on $n \geq 2$. Suppose there is a nonzero f in $B(V)$. We must show $\kappa = n = 2$ and $f = \det$.

Let e_1, \dots, e_n be a basis of V , and set $a := f(e_1, e_1), b := f(e_1, e_2)$. By invariance we have $f(v, v) = a$ for all $v \neq 0$, and $f(v, w) = b$ for all linearly independent v and w ; in particular $(a, b) \neq (0, 0)$. We have

$$b = f(e_1, e_1 + e_2) = f(e_1, e_1) + f(e_1, e_2) = a + b \implies a = 0 \neq b.$$

For $0 \neq \lambda \in K$ we have $b = f(e_1, \lambda e_2) = \lambda b$, hence $\lambda = 1$, hence $\kappa = 2$, hence $b = 1$, hence $f = \det$ if $n = 2$. If $n \geq 3$ we have

$$1 = f(e_1, e_2 + e_3) = f(e_1, e_2) + f(e_1, e_3) = 1 + 1 = 0,$$

contradiction. This completes the proof.

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